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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF
GALANTAMINE PATCHES FOR TRANSDERMAL DRUG
DELIVERY SYSTEM****Chiramala Likhitha¹, K.Kishore², Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar³**^{1,2,3}KGR Institute of Technology And Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy,
Telangana, India.**Abstract**

In present study transdermal drug delivery of Galantamine was developed to overcome the first pass metabolism and to reduce frequency of dosing compared to oral route. Matrix type of transdermal patches were developed by using polymers Eudragit-L100, HPMCK₄M and HPMCK₁₅M. Transdermal patches were prepared by employing solvent casting method. Propylene glycol and Tween80 were selected as permeation enhancer and plasticizer. Formulations were prepared by taking Eudragit-L100, HPMCK₄M, HPMCK₁₅M as polymers in the concentrations of 100 mg, 150 mg and 200 mg from F1-F9 formulations, Eudragit-L100 100mg and HPMCK₄M 100mg in F10, Eudragit-L100 100mg and HPMCK₁₅M 100mg in F11, HPMCK₄M 100mg and HPMCK₁₅M 100mg in F12, all the formulations were evaluated for various physical parameters, invitro drug release studies by using dialysis membrane. Among all the formulations F6 formulation was found to be best and shown 96.5% drug release in 12 hours. For F6 formulation release kinetics were applied and it was observed that the formulation was following peppas mechanism of drug release. Drug excipient compatibility studies were carried out by using FTIR, and it was observed that they were no interactions.

Keywords: Galantamine, Transdermal patch, Eudragit-L100, HPMCK₄M and HPMCK₁₅M**Corresponding author:****Kamere Kishore**

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INTRODUCTION:

Transdermal therapeutic systems are defined as self-contained discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug(s), through the skin, at controlled rate to the systemic circulation (USP 25). Transdermal patch is a medicated adhesive pad that is designed to release the active ingredient at a constant rate over a period of several hours to days after application to the skin. It is also called skin patch. A transdermal patch uses a special membrane to control the rate at which the drug contained within the patch can pass through the skin and into the bloodstream. Often, this promotes healing to an injured area of the body. An advantage of a transdermal drug delivery route over other types of medication delivery such as oral, topical, intravenous, intramuscular, etc. is that the patch provides a controlled release of the medication into the patient, usually through either a porous membrane covering a reservoir of medication or through body heat melting thin layers of medication embedded in the adhesive. The main disadvantage to transdermal delivery systems stems from the fact that the skin is a very effective barrier; as a result, only medications whose molecules are small enough to penetrate the skin can be delivered in this method.

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common form of dementia. It is a neurological disease characterized by loss of mental ability, severe enough to interfere with normal activities of daily living. AD usually occurs in old age, and is marked by a decline in cognitive functions such as remembering, reasoning, and planning. The median survival time for affected patients is approximately 8 yrs from the onset of

symptoms. Galantamine is a tertiary alkaloid and a reversible, competitive acetyl cholinesterase inhibitor. It is effective and well tolerated for symptomatic treatment of AD. It improves cognition, global function and daily life activities of the patients. At present, galantamine is available in the market as tablet or oral solution. Oral administration of galantamine is followed by side effects like abdominal pain, nausea, and diarrhea. Therefore, an alternative way of galantamine administration could be helpful for the success of therapy.

MATERIALS:

Galantamine, Distilled water, Ethanol, Eudragit L-100, HPMCK15M, HPMCK4M, Methanol all the chemicals used were lab grade

METHODOLOGY FORMULATION:**Development of Transdermal patches:**

Transdermal drug delivery patches were prepared by solvent casting method.

Transdermal patches were prepared according to the formula shown in Table 08. Eudragit L100, HPMCK4M and HPMCK15M were weighed in requisite ratios and they were then dissolved in dichloromethane and ethanol as solvent using magnetic stirrer. Galantamine (300 mg), Propylene glycol and Tween 80 was added to the above dispersion under continuous stirring. The uniform dispersion was poured in the petri plate. The rate of evaporation of solvent was controlled by inverting cut funnel over the patches. After 24h, the dried films were taken out and stored in desiccator.

Table 1: Formulations of Galantamine Transdermal Patch

S.No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
1	Drug(mg)	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
2	Eudragit-L100(mg)	100	150	200	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	100	-
3	HPMCK ₄ M(mg)	-	-	-	100	150	200	-	-	-	100	-	100
4	HPMCK ₁₅ M(mg)	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	150	200	-	100	100
5	Dichloromethane(ml)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
6	Ethanol(ml)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
7	Propylene glycol(ml)	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
8	Tween-80(ml)	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2

Evaluation Of Prepared patches

The designed patches were evaluated for physical appearance, thickness, weight variation, flatness, folding endurance, moisture uptake, moisture content, drug content determination, surface pH surface pH, In vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Table : 2 Standard graph of Galantamine

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (nm)
5	0.123
10	0.210
15	0.320
20	0.411
25	0.501

Figure. 1 : Standard curve of Galantamine**Evaluation of Galantamine Transdermal patches****Table 3 : Evaluation of Transdermal patch by physical methods**

Formulation	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Drug content (%)	Moisture uptake (%)	Moisture content (%)
F1	0.3569	20	45	7.98	3.77
F2	0.3520	25	65	25.05	9.2
F3	0.3470	27	57.5	13.09	5.16
F4	0.3496	24	60	15.63	5.66
F5	0.3460	30	67.5	11.73	4.87
F6	0.3517	32	92.5	19.65	12.67
F7	0.3478	40	101.7	9.42	3.43
F8	0.3437	37	85	10.87	4.72
F9	0.3503	34	55	16.44	6.62
F10	0.3532	29	62.5	13.08	6.17

F11	0.3546	26	85	20.63	7.94
F12	0.3503	31	82.5	15.73	6.55

Table 4 : Evaluation of Transdermal patch by In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

Time (hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
1	9.05	15.1	10.1	9.49	10.9	20.2	17.5	12.0	11.1	12.7	10.0	20.4
2	13.3	19.8	12.8	11.3	19.6	27.8	21.9	17.5	13.0	17.9	12.5	25.4
4	14.6	28.3	21.5	22.6	24.9	42.8	33.5	23.4	23.3	27.4	23.6	33.0
6	21.9	34.1	25.9	32.3	31.2	53.5	40.0	30.9	33.4	32.7	30.9	41.7
8	32.7	41.1	33.4	33.9	38.0	66.3	46.5	48.1	52.7	50.6	36.7	47.9
10	40.4	50.1	44.5	56.3	50.3	82.0	64.2	60.0	66.4	63.0	45.9	63.0
12	54.2	65.8	56.7	69.4	65.9	96.5	91.9	78.7	79.1	74.8	56	80.9

Figure 2 : Release profile of In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

Table 5 : kinetics of In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

CUMULATIVE TIME (%) RELEASE	ROOT (T) (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN
0	0	0		2.000
20.2	0.5	0.707	1.305	-0.301
27.8	1	1.000	1.444	0.000
42.8	2	1.414	1.631	0.301
53.5	3	1.732	1.728	0.477
66.3	4	2.000	1.822	0.602
82.0	5	2.236	1.914	0.699
96.5	6	2.449	1.985	0.778

Figure 3 : Zero order kinetics

Figure 4 : Higuchi plot

Figure 5 : Peppas plot

Figure 6 : First order kinetics

CONCLUSION:

In present study transdermal drug delivery of Galantamine was developed to overcome the first pass metabolism and to reduce frequency of dosing compared to oral route. Oral drug delivery system has various drawbacks like poor bioavailability due to hepatic metabolism (first pass) and the tendency to produce rapid blood level spikes (both high and low), leading to a need for high and/or frequent dosing, which can be both cost prohibitive and inconvenient. Matrix type of transdermal patches was developed by using polymers Eudragit-L100, HPMCK4M and HPMCK15M. Transdermal patches were prepared by employing solvent casting method. Propylene glycol and Tween80 were selected as permeation enhancer and plasticizer. Drug excipient compatibility studies were carried out by using FTIR, and it was observed that there were no interactions.

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